

Composite sandwich optimization of a stiffened panel structure

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Knowledge for Tomorrow

Sandwich composites in aerospace design

Status

- Offer increased bending stiffness at low weight cost
- Used in secondary sub-structures – fairings, ailerons, flaps, rudders

- Potential problems
 - Damage tolerance
 - Manufacturing complexity
 - Moisture ingestion
 - Additional failure modes

Aim of this work

- To present a strategy for the optimization of sandwich composites for practical problems
 - To study potential weight gains over conventional laminate designs
 - Potentially justify research aimed at studying/overcoming limitations of sandwich composites
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- 1) New lamination parameter scheme applicable to sandwich composites and in general, multi-material composites
 - 2) Account for sandwich failure modes in a simple yet adequate manner

Failure modes considered

- Buckling – (MSC.NASTRAN)
- Facesheet failure – AML criterion
- Shear crimping, facesheet wrinkling – CMH-17

Example – stiffened plate

- Stiffened cantilever plate with a tip load
- Stiffener properties kept a constant
- 24 patches in total optimized
- Design variables – lamination parameters and thickness of the patches

Example – stiffened plate

- Optimized mass of monolithic laminate design = 10.2 kg
- Optimized mass of sandwich design = 6.60kg
 - All patches at minimum gauge
 - One IDEAL scenario for application of sandwiches

Example – stiffened plate

- Chosen example is slightly biased – buckling-dominated problem
- Next steps – apply methods to solve more-realistic wing-type loading problem to quantify gains

Conclusions and outlook

- A new parametrization scheme for sandwich composites, extendable to multi-material composites is presented
- An in-house optimization framework for composites design is presented
- The proposed scheme is tested on a stiffened cantilever plate example

- Using a more realistic buckling-strength balanced problem for comparison
- Including more failure modes like dimpling, core-crushing
- Including practical constraints such as laminate blending

Thank you for your attention!

Questions?

DLR

- DLR (German Aerospace Center) is a national center for aerospace, energy and transportation research
- approximately 8000 employees at 16 sites
- 23 research institutes
- founded in 1907 as “Aerodynamische Versuchsanstalt” in Göttingen, Director: Ludwig Prandtl
- Institute of Aeroelasticity in Göttingen

